

Techniques for deprescribing potentially inappropriate medications for the elderly in primary care - A systematic review.

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Review methods were amended after registration. Please see the revision notes and previous versions for detail.

Citation

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Review question

Taking into account that in primary care we have high complexity in terms of care and low technological density, what would be the best approach to carry out long-term Deprescribing of potentially inappropriate medications for elderly people in primary care?

Searches

PubMed, Embase, LILACS.

Types of study to be included

Randomized Clinical Trials (RCT).

Condition or domain being studied

Deprescribing is the planned and supervised process of dose reduction or stopping of medication that might be causing harm, or no longer be of benefit. Deprescribing is part of good prescribing – backing off when doses are too high, or stopping medications that are no longer needed.

Participants/population

People in elderly, defined by 65 years old or more in developed countries and 60 years old or more in development countries. Exclusion: Patients in palliative or end-life care.

Intervention(s), exposure(s)

Deprescribing techniques, defined as techniques focused on the deprescribing of potentially inappropriate medications in the elderly, in different settings and with an emphasis on primary care.

Comparator(s)/control

Usual care or orientations only.

Main outcome(s)

Long-term Deprescribing.

Additional outcome(s)

Hospital admission and mortality.

Data extraction (selection and coding)

Duplicates will be removed. Two reviewers will independently screen titles and abstracts of records to determine whether they potentially meet the inclusion criteria. Next, full-texts of potentially eligible studies will be obtained and further examined by two reviewers against the inclusion criteria to determine eligibility. Discrepancies will be resolved by discussion. The data will be extracted by using Covidence tool.

Risk of bias (quality) assessment [1 change]

The risk of bias will be assessed by two reviewers independently using the RoB 2.0 (Revised Cochrane risk-of-bias tool for randomized trials).

Strategy for data synthesis

Data will be analysed descriptively by medication groups and/or intervention types. For primary outcome: Proportions of patients (with 95% confidence intervals) whose drug cessation remains at 6 months or longer;

Prevalence % (with 95% confidence interval) of patients on potentially inappropriate medications (as defined by each study) at 6 months or longer.

For secondary outcome: Mortality rates % (with 95% CI) and Hospital re-admission rates % (with 95% CI) in the first year post-intervention.

Analysis of subgroups or subsets

No subgroup analysis was planned.

Contact details for further information

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Organisational affiliation of the review

Universidade Federal de Uberlândia

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Review team members and their organisational affiliations [1 change]

Mr Emanuel Oliveira. Universidade Federal de Uberlândia

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Mr Luan Carrijo. Universidade Federal de Uberlândia

Type and method of review

Intervention, Narrative synthesis, Prognostic, Systematic review

Anticipated or actual start date

08 August 2022

Anticipated completion date

28 June 2024

Funding sources/sponsors

Universidade Federal de Uberlândia, a public University from Brazil, acting in teaching, research and extension, and important social function in the City of Uberlândia, state of Minas Gerais, Brazil. Named the third best university in the state of Minas Gerais and one of the top 30 universities in Brazil by the QS World University Rankings 2023, considering academic reputation; reputation among employers; teacher/student ratio; scientific citations; proportion of foreign students; international faculty; international research network; and employability.

Conflicts of interest

Language

English, Portuguese-Brazil

Country

Brazil

Stage of review

Review Ongoing

Subject index terms status

Subject indexing assigned by CRD

Subject index terms

Aged; Deprescriptions; Humans; Inappropriate Prescribing; Polypharmacy; Potentially Inappropriate Medication List; Technology

Date of registration in PROSPERO

27 April 2023

Date of first submission

16 April 2023

Stage of review at time of this submission

Stage	Started	Completed
Preliminary searches	Yes	No
Piloting of the study selection process	Yes	No
Formal screening of search results against eligibility criteria	No	No
Data extraction	No	No
Risk of bias (quality) assessment	No	No
Data analysis	No	No

Revision note

Correcting spelling errors and updating information.

The record owner confirms that the information they have supplied for this submission is accurate and complete and they understand that deliberate provision of inaccurate information or omission of data may be construed as scientific misconduct.

The record owner confirms that they will update the status of the review when it is completed and will add publication details in due course.

Versions

27 April 2023

27 April 2023

28 April 2023

28 April 2023